

Remarks on Metabolic Health Conference 2024: In light of personal experience and scientific literature

Abhinav Vitthalrao Pathare ^[1] ^{[2]*}; Anup Bhaskarrao Chaudhary ^[3] ^[4]

¹ Master of Science in Applied Public Health, The University of Central Lancashire (UCLan), England

² Principal Investigator, Public Health India (PHI), Mumbai, India

³ Director & Chief Nutrition Advisor, Public Health India (PHI), Mumbai, India

⁴ Senior Lecturer in Nutrition Sciences, India

OPEN ACCESS

Corresponding Author

Abhinav Vitthalrao Pathare

Master of Science in Applied Public Health, The University of Central Lancashire (UCLan), England

Principal Investigator, Public Health India (PHI), Mumbai, India

Received: 10-05-2024

Accepted: 25-05-2024

Available online: 06-06-2024

©Copyright: IJMPR Journal

ABSTRACT

This article aims to provide a remark on the second Metabolic Health Conference (MHC-2), which was recently held from April 26 to 28, 2024. The authors are researchers who participated in MHC-2 as speakers and wanted to provide a remark which should reach diverse professionals and members of the public. The authors formulate this remark by using their personal experience at the conference and critically reflecting on the relevant scientific literature. This article finds the following.

While India needs novel approaches to address its increasing metabolic health issues, and while adopting such approaches is challenging, the Metabolic Health Conferences (MHCs) serve as a promising hope. Moreover, the first Metabolic Health Conference (MHC-1) and MHC-2 fill the gap of roughly 115 years, as within this span, it is hard to find a conference exclusively dedicated to discussing the low-carbohydrate approach in light of diabetes and metabolic syndrome in India.

Additionally, because of MHC-1 and MHC-2, for the first time in the history of the Indian low-carbohydrate movement, numerous stakeholders—researchers, doctors, health professionals, and organisations—across the globe united to discuss the low-carbohydrate approach in light of the Indian population's diverse metabolic health issues. These conferences are an essential resource for contemporary and future researchers and practitioners. Therefore, MHC-1 and MHC-2 are pivotal in reshaping Indian public health.

Keywords: *Metabolic health conference, MHC, MHC-1, MHC-2, Anup Singh, Ira Sahay, Shashikant Iyengar, low-carbohydrate, India, public health.*

1) Introduction.

1.1) Opening message: First of all...

Dear Anup Singh, Ira Sahay, and Shashikant Iyengar (ordered alphabetically), we congratulate you and your brilliant team on successfully conducting the second Metabolic Health Conference (MHC-2). The efforts you all have put into making this historic event successful are commendable. Your utmost care of every minute detail while conducting the conference is exemplary. The ease at which you conducted the conference for the entire three days depicts the precision of your planning.

Your work inspires us all. We applaud your and your team's efforts. We hope to see many more landmark conferences in the future and wish you all the best in your endeavours. We wish you more power and thank you for warmly inviting and welcoming us to MHC-2. We are pleased to write this article, presenting our remarks and a brief review of MHC-2.

1.2) Adopting novel approaches: A challenge to India.

India has been facing the rising tide of metabolic syndrome for years (Bhalwar, 2020) ^[1], which is a severe public health issue. Mainstream efforts are being made to address this issue (Kar & Kar, 2015) ^[3]. However, the fact that India is

often referred to as the diabetes capital of the world (Pandey & Sharma, 2018) ^[12] suggests the scope for improvement in the current efforts.

Novel efforts are urgently needed to address the epidemic of metabolic syndrome in India (Narayan et al., 2023) ^[11]. However, India faces numerous challenges, including—but not limited to—the information-seeking behaviours of health professionals (Pathare, 2023a) ^[16], symptomatic treatment approaches (Times of India, 2024) ^[21], overreliance on pharmaceutical interventions and irrational drug prescriptions (Gadre, 2015) ^[2], longstanding beliefs and a reluctance to embrace culturally and conventionally less accepted methods (like low-carbohydrate approaches). These challenges curb India's ability to adopt novel and comprehensive approaches.

2) Landmark initiative: The Metabolic Health Conference (MHC).

A substantial body of evidence suggests that the low-carbohydrate approach effectively manages various metabolic issues and promotes a healthy lifestyle (Volek et al., 2024) ^[22]. However, because of the challenges mentioned in the introduction section, this approach remains primarily unacknowledged by most (if not all) current mainstream professionals and policymakers, limiting its reach to the Indian public.

It is imperative to increase the reach of the low-carbohydrate approach to the Indian public and professionals through various channels to help people make informed decisions about their lifestyles. One of the most promising ways to communicate this information is through conferences—Shashikant Iyengar, Anup Singh, Ira Sahay, and their exceptional team are pivotal in this direction. They spread this vital information through their MHC initiative. So far, two editions of this conference have been conducted: MHC-1, conducted in 2023, and MHC-2, conducted in 2024.

3) Filling the gap of 115 years: Significance of Metabolic Health Conferences (MHCs).

The British Medical Association's conference was held in 1907 (roughly 115 years ago) in Exeter, United Kingdom. This conference had a dedicated session on "Diabetes in the Tropics"—one of the first occasions when Indian diabetes received importance in the West (Mohan et al., 2021) ^[10].

Since this conference till today, many conferences must be held in light of Indian diabetes. However, there was a significant gap, and we want to signify this gap by asking a question to the readers of this article: within the span of roughly 115 years (from 1907 to 2022), could you find a conference which was exclusively dedicated to discussing low-carbohydrate approach in light of Indian diabetes? If you can find it, you can inform us, and if you cannot, then this 115-year gap seems to be filled in 2023 by MHC-1 (followed by MHC-2 in 2024).

4) Transforming the Indian public health: Significance of MHCs.

The implications of MHCs are far-reaching. For instance, the MHC-2, themed "Metabolic Therapies", brought together leading low-carbohydrate researchers and practitioners worldwide, each with unique expertise in various medical and public health disciplines. Their diverse backgrounds and extensive experiences provided credibility to the information shared at the conference.

These professionals shared their understanding, enormous knowledge, and experience of how a low-carbohydrate approach effectively manages the respective metabolic disorders, implying the importance of this approach in the current Indian public health scenario. This suggests that the implications of the discussions held through MHC-2 are enormous in light of the Indian public and health professionals, helping them to constructively rethink the current mainstream advice and dietary guidelines, take necessary steps towards addressing the epidemic of metabolic syndrome, and devise effective public health strategies.

5) A unique resource for researchers and practitioners: Significance of MHCs.

The implications of this conference on the contemporary and future generations of metabolic health researchers and practitioners are enormous. They will regard this conference as one of the most resourceful databases when searching historical data on the Indian low-carbohydrate context. The diverse and excellent speakers worldwide sharing their views and remedies provide knowledge that can be implemented for better Indian public health outcomes. The archives of MHC-1 and MHC-2 are available on YouTube. For MHC-1 links, see Metabolic Health India (2023a, 2023b, 2023c) ^{[4] [5] [6]}, and for MHC-2 links, see Metabolic Health India (2024a, 2024b, 2024c) ^{[7] [8] [9]} in the reference list.

6) Conclusion.

India needs novel approaches to combat the rising issue of metabolic syndrome. However, adopting such approaches is challenging for India for varying reasons, such as health professionals' information-seeking behaviours, overreliance on pharmaceutical interventions and symptomatic treatments, longstanding beliefs, and a reluctance to embrace culturally and conventionally less accepted methods. Nevertheless, MHCs demonstrate remarkable effort and promising hope. MHCs fill the longstanding gap of more than a century—within the span of 115 years, it is difficult to find a conference exclusively dedicated to discussing the low-carbohydrate approach in light of the Indian population's diabetes and metabolic issues.

The implications of MHCs for Indian public health are enormous. They will be one of the cornerstones of evidence for the low-carbohydrate movement in India, serving as a meaningful resource for the contemporary and future generations of researchers and practitioners.

7) About authors.

Both authors were invited to MHC-2 to present their research paper titled: "2.5-Month effects of a high-intensity low-carbohydrate intervention on glycemic and lipid profile: A type-2 diabetes near-to-remission case study of a 65-year-old Indian woman with recent bilateral knee replacement surgery" (Pathare & Chaudhary, 2024) [20]. This paper is the first of its kind in the history of Indian medical and public health literature. The MHC committee likely asserts that this research paper is the first *published* record of a diabetes remission case study in light of the low-carbohydrate intervention on an Indian participant.

7.1) About Abhinav Vitthalrao Pathare.

Abhinav V Pathare is a public health researcher from India. In 2020, he received a Master of Science in Applied Public Health from the University of Central Lancashire, England, with merit classification. His master's thesis focused on facilitating low-carbohydrate policies in the United Kingdom's National Dietary Guidelines (NDGs) and received distinction. He serves as a Principal Investigator in low-carbohydrate-related contemporary research projects.

Abhinav has written multiple journal articles and editorials on various public health and medical topics (Pathare & Chaudhary, 2022a, 2022b, 2024; Pathare, 2021a, 2021b, 2022, 2023a, 2023b) [18] [19] [20] [14] [15] [13] [16] [17]. Abhinav aims to improve public health outcomes through informed policies, strategies, interventions, and communication techniques. He advocates the Whole System Approach for facilitating low-carbohydrate-supportive policies, encouraging the interdisciplinary and collaborative approach.

7.2) About Anup Bhaskarrao Chaudhary.

Anup Bhaskarrao Chaudhary is an Indian researcher in nutrition sciences. He has published multiple research papers in scholarly journals (Pathare & Chaudhary, 2022a, 2022b, 2024) [18] [19] [20]. Anup is also the Founding Director of Public Health India (PHI), an Indian health advocacy organisation, and a consultant nutritionist who helps a wide range of populations to improve metabolic health and quality of life.

Anup aims to bring India-specific low-carbohydrate data into the literature to help public health researchers, mainstream health professionals, and health organisations make informed decisions in designing and improving treatment strategies for better metabolic outcomes in the members of the public.

8) Authors' contribution.

Both authors contributed equally to this manuscript and were involved in carefully proofreading the content and approving the manuscript for publication.

9) Authors' ORCID iDs.

Abhinav V Pathare: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4811-0121>

Anup B Chaudhary: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0035-1436>

10) Conflict of interest.

There is no conflict of interest. The authors are not—formally or currently—affiliated with or associated with any element of the MHC. There has been no financial support for this article that could have influenced the outcomes.

11) Dedication statement.

This article is dedicated to the entire MHC team—each and every member.

12) Acknowledgement.

We thank the MHC decision-makers for inviting us to such a prestigious conference.

13) References.

- 1) Bhalwar, R. (2020). Metabolic syndrome: The Indian public health perspective. *medical journal armed forces India*, 76(1), 8-16. <https://doi.org/10.1016%2Fj.mjafi.2019.12.001>
- 2) Gadre, A. (2015). India's private healthcare sector treats patients as revenue generators. *Bmj*, 350. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.h826>
- 3) Kar, S. S., & Kar, S. S. (2015). Prevention of childhood obesity in India: Way forward. *Journal of natural science, biology, and medicine*, 6(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.4103%2F0976-9668.149071>
- 4) Metabolic Health India. (2023a). *Metabolic health conference – Day 1*. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/live/nSO9v5EJwvE?feature=shared>

- 5) Metabolic Health India. (2023b). *Metabolic health conference – Day 2*. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/live/rxUAaB6nPSY?feature=shared>
- 6) Metabolic Health India. (2023c). *Metabolic health conference – Day 3*. Retrieved from https://www.youtube.com/live/y22HeshH_6g?feature=shared
- 7) Metabolic Health India. (2024a). *Day 1 of 2nd metabolic health conference – India*. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eA7wfpsNW3s>
- 8) Metabolic Health India. (2024b). *Day 2 of 2nd metabolic health conference – India*. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5cxOF78-BTQ>
- 9) Metabolic Health India. (2024c). *Day 3 of 2nd metabolic health conference – India*. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HyqbAmNhK1g>
- 10) Mohan, V., Bhavadharini, B., Mukhopadhyay, S., Nallaperumal, S., Tiwaskar, M., Anjana, R. M., & Unnikrishnan, R. (2021). Diabetes in pre-independence India: Rediscovering a forgotten era. *Journal of the Association of Physicians of India*, 69, 80-84. PMID: 34472814
- 11) Narayan, K. V., Varghese, J. S., Beyh, Y. S., Bhattacharyya, S., Khandelwal, S., Krishnan, G. S., ... & Kurpad, A. V. (2023). A Strategic Research Framework for Defeating Diabetes in India: A 21st-Century Agenda. *Journal of the Indian Institute of Science*, 103(1), 33-54. <https://doi.org/10.1007%2Fs41745-022-00354-5>
- 12) Pandey, S. K., & Sharma, V. (2018). World diabetes day 2018: battling the emerging epidemic of diabetic retinopathy. *Indian journal of ophthalmology*, 66(11), 1652-1653. https://doi.org/10.4103%2Fijo.IJO_1681_18
- 13) Pathare, A. (2022). Mr Kaizzad Capadia: "The Science Protector" Like Dr Burwell from Harvard and Dr Sackett from Oxford University. *International Journal of Medical Science and Current Research*, 5(1), 428-431. Retrieved from <http://www.ijmscr.com/asset/images/uploads/16431823710447.pdf>
- 14) Pathare, A. V. (2021a). Exercise Does Not Solve Obesity: The "Calorie-Burning Theory" Is Misleading And Incorrect. *International Journal Dental and Medical Sciences Research*, 3(5), 328-333. Retrieved from <http://clok.uclan.ac.uk/39920/1/39920%20AbhinavIJDMSR Article Editorial.pdf>
- 15) Pathare, A. V. (2021b). Healthy Setting Approach: Origin, Evolution, and Development; Challenges and Opportunities in the University Setting. *International Journal of Medical Science and Current Research (IJMSCR)*, 4(5), 1069-1080. <https://clok.uclan.ac.uk/39919/1/39919%20HealthySettingAbhinavArticle.pdf>
- 16) Pathare, A. V. (2023a). Medical interventions and their poor scientific backup: A threat to Evidence-Based Medicine. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Medicine*, 5(2), 117-120. <https://doi.org/10.22271/27069567.2023.v5.i2b.488>
- 17) Pathare, A. V. (2023b). Improving the support for older adults in India: A multi-faceted approach for a better future. *International Journal of Paediatrics and Geriatrics*, 6(2), 13-17. <https://doi.org/10.33545/26643685.2023.v6.i2a.206>
- 18) Pathare, A. V., & Chaudhary, A. B. (2022a). Contemporary directions in fatty liver disease in light of low-carbohydrate approach: a review by public health India. *European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine*, 9(2), 808–817. <http://publichealthindia.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Ejmcm-2263.1.pdf>
- 19) Pathare, A. V., & Chaudhary, A. B. (2022b). War and public health: Relevancies and competencies explained by 'Public Health India'. *International Journal of Advanced Community Medicine*, 5(3), 05-07. <https://doi.org/10.33545/comed.2022.v5.i3a.240>
- 20) Pathare, A. V., & Chaudhary, A. B. (2024). 2.5-Month effects of a high-intensity low-carbohydrate intervention on glycemic and lipid profile: A type-2 diabetes near-to-remission case study of a 65-year-old Indian woman with recent bilateral knee replacement surgery. *Journal of population therapeutics and clinical pharmacology*. 31(3), 1398-1415. <https://doi.org/10.53555/jptcp.v31i3.5141>
- 21) Times of India. (2024). *The importance of addressing root causes of illness rather than just symptoms*. Retrieved from <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/life-style/health-fitness/health-news/the-importance-of-addressing-root-causes-of-illness-rather-than-just-symptoms/articleshow/109135016.cms>
- 22) Volek, J. S., Yancy Jr, W. S., Gower, B. A., Phinney, S. D., Slavin, J., Koutnik, A. P., ... & Hecht, F. M. (2024). Expert consensus on nutrition and lower-carbohydrate diets: An evidence-and equity-based approach to dietary guidance. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 11, 1376098. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2024.1376098>